

THE ROLE OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN FIELD OF CADASTRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682825>

Abstract. *This article presents some new information about the role of modern information technologies in the field of cadastre. New ways of land registration by introducing information technologies into the field of cadastre are explained in detail. Detailed information was given about the great opportunities for importing and using modern information technologies in the field of cadastre in our country.*

Keywords: *cadastre, information, technology, code, field, registration, systematization, modeling.*

Development of modern information technologies in the field of cadastre, if we systematically analyze the cadastral field in our country, first of all, the policy carried out in our country, ease of use of information technologies, favorable opportunities for land registration, full provision of legal freedom and it is caused by several other factors. Nowadays, no field can be imagined without modern information technologies.

After our country gained independence, changes were made in many areas, including the cadastral area. For example, in the field of cadastre, the use of modern information technologies, digitalization, creation of a regenerative model and algorithm make it possible to fully illuminate land registration, quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Among them, the use of modern methods in the process of land registration and its application to the general public, the use of the latest methods in determining quantity and quality indicators.

As the main technical tool of the field of modern information technology and mathematical modeling, I think it is appropriate to perform computational organizational operations, systematic analysis, decision-making algorithms, to apply this to the cadastral field, that is, to measure land areas and assign numbers to them.

Nowadays, modern information technologies are widely used all over the world in digitalization, algorithmization, programming, and modeling of all fields. Therefore, it is appropriate to use these processes in the field of cadastre, that is, to use them in cadastre types such as urban planning, state land cadastre, state highway cadastre in our country.

It is obvious that the question arises as to how this will be done. For example, the state cadastre of flora, including the area occupied by plants, their registration, geographical location, and the use of plant types for precise and quick identification.

We think it is appropriate to eliminate mutual conflicts between legal entities and individuals in the state land cadastre, to reduce the human factor, and to use the most modern information technologies.

Summarizing the points made above, we make the following suggestions:

- Cultivation of all vacant and abandoned lands in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- To reduce the area of permanently cultivated crops in the territory of the Republic and to establish rotation;
- Establishing the use of modern technologies in land registration in the territory of the Republic;
- Delivering industry-related materials to personnel in a modern way through information technologies;
- Studying the geographical location, geographical situation and quantitative and qualitative indicators of the territory through modern telecommunication tools;
- In collecting and using cadastral data and information, applying the legal documents and normative documents "On State Cadastres" through modern information media;
- Use of information technologies in state registration of property rights and other rights to cadastral objects;
- Use of modern information technologies in the introduction of geographical location, geographical condition and qualitative indicators of any territory into the unified state cadastral system;
- Appropriation and digitization of remote areas, regions, abandoned lands through innovative technologies;
- Cadastre field online: algorithmization, programming, modeling, regenerative model building;

We noted above that there are great opportunities in the use and development of modern information technologies in the field of cadastre in our country. It is possible to achieve the goal only if these opportunities are properly directed. One of the main factors in the development of information technologies in the field of cadastre is the reduction of the human factor and the introduction of more digital technologies. It is desirable to train young personnel studying in the field of cadastre on the basis of modern information technologies. In studying the field, it is desirable to exchange training with foreign experience, to gain experience, to carry out automated registration of land measurements.

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